

Assessing the Profitability Analysis of Family Poultry Farming on Southern Micro Region of Bangladesh

Muhammad Rabi Ullah

“Associate Professor” Department of Economics Gopalganj Science and Technology University Gopalganj-8105, Bangladesh

ABSTRACT: Many studies have been done on family poultry farming and its impact on farmer’s life in Bangladesh. The present study is undertaken to examine socio-economic features of family poultry farmer, the impact of family poultry on household improvement, and to determine cost, return and profitability through family poultry farming. Identification of problems faced by family poultry farmer and solutions are suggested in this study. The data were collected from 60 poultry farm’s families from southern micro zone on Gopalganj Sadar Upazila in Gopalganj district through direct interview method by a well-structured questionnaire during the month of January – June 2025. As analytical tools simple statistical measures, Cobb Douglas production function was used to observe the impact of explanatory variables on gross return. In the selected area maximum people are related with agriculture. It was found that family poultry farming was chosen by 100% farmers as subsidiary occupation. The result of the study shows that, the average gross return, gross cost and net return of family poultry farms were Tk. 7582, Tk. 3880.49 and Tk. 4101.51 respectively. The Benefit cost ratio was 1.95. Therefore, family poultry farm is highly profitable. The study also determined the impact of family poultry production on livelihood of poultry farmers. The income of 78% poultry farms has increased and for savings, it was 30%. It is also found from the study that the livelihood of 77% poultry farmers has improved through family in the study area. Finally, based on the findings of the study, some recommendations were made for the development of family poultry production in Bangladesh.

KEYWORDS: Profitability, Poultry firm, Micro level Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Bangladesh mainly depends on its agricultural sector and this sector is divided into various sub-sectors. Among various sub-sectors livestock is one of the most important sub-sectors in the economy. At present livestock contributes 3.40% to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2017-2018. Livestock especially poultry contributes significantly to the welfare of the people both at household level and national level. Overall, the annual average growth in poultry production from 2009 to 2016 was 3.9% (BER, 2016). Among poultries family poultry rising is common in the rural communities of low-income countries. In Bangladesh 90% of rural households raise poultry (Sultana et al., 2012) and traditionally women and children are the raisers of these birds (Huque, 1999). Family poultry enables the poor farmers without substantial amounts of land, training and capital to earn income from birds scavenging on common property, village land or fed household waste. It has been shown as an important source of cash income to families in Asia (Ramm et al., 1984) and Latin America (Rauen et al., 1990).

There are three production systems for family poultry - free range; backyard and small- scale intensive with productivity of 20-60, 30-100 and 80-150 eggs/hen/year, respectively. The production system for indigenous chickens is smallholder backyard scavenging in nature with each family keeping an average of 6-7 chickens to meet family requirements and from which a cash income can also be derived when necessary. The non-descript Deshi chicken constitutes about 90% of the indigenous population. Also known as ‘Murghi’ they have undergone unknown periods of natural selection and are a reservoir of excellent genetic diversity (Bhuiyan et al., 2005).

The Bangladesh Rural Poultry Development Program (BRPDP) clearly showed that families without poultry were poorer than those with poultry (Jensen, 1996).

Thus the present study attempted to examine income generation, factors affecting income generation, to inspect employment generation, to observe the impact of family poultry on livelihood improvement and to identify the problems faced by family poultry farmers. Raising poultry birds is mostly a subsistence practice in Bangladesh. The contribution of poultry production is vital to the national economy in case of generating employment opportunity, additional income for households and improving the nutritional level of the people. The present meat and egg production can meet only 68% and 64% of the national demand. For the development of the agrarian and largely subsistence economy of the country livestock and poultry sectors plays an important role.

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The situation of family poultry production was implied by the term family poultry. A number of technologies for increasing productivity and contributed substantially to generate income and reduce poverty, women empowerment and nutritional enhancement for building a poverty free and healthy society family poultry production system has introduced. In addition to providing opportunities to increase poultry exports, rising poultry production spurs growth in global import demand for feeds and other inputs and livelihood improvement through poultry farming investment opportunities in this sector. Meat is an excellent source of protein. Family poultry ensures the availability of poultry meat to the rural poor who suffer from malnutrition. Poultry meat is cheaper than beef, mutton, etc. It is generally accepted by all religion and casts. The poultry meat is also digestible with less fat comparatively with other animals. Family poultry production provides balance protein and income opportunities for the family.

For the improvement of the livelihood of poor farmers small scale family poultry plays an important role. By providing balance diet and helps in poverty alleviation in rural areas it is well accepted. The village women are generally kept family poultry. A remarkable change for the family was undertaken by family poultry. The livelihood pattern also improved by it. Balance nutrition among children of these families also maintained by family poultry. Earning from family poultry has a potential impact on total income of the poor farmer and helps to make better choice. Under these circumstances the study was done to identify the socio-economic features of family poultry, to examine the impact of family poultry on household improvement, to identify the problems faced by family poultry farmer and for its improvement.

HISTORY OF POULTRY

Four thousand years is a fair old time for chickens to have been domesticated. They originate from the Red Jungle Fowl (*Gallus*, a small pheasant of Asia) and have provided us with eggs, fresh meat and feathers plus some truly horrible traditional medicines. Domestic ducks are all descended from the lascivious ubiquitous mallard (*Anas platyrhynchos*) and domestic geese from the tame and confiding graylag (*Anser anser*) which in return for a little corn would have provided meat, eggs and excellent fletching for arrow flights from the mounted wing feathers when the bow was a common weapon. Turkeys originated in Central and North America and the various pretty colors come from the different subspecies ranging from Mexico up to New England. Chicken provides 20% of the world's animal protein at a reasonable price – what a huge debt the human race owes the humble domestic fowl.

BANGLADESH (KEY DATA FROM 2023-2024)

- **Production Surge:** Milk, meat, and egg output nearly tripled in a decade, with 2022-23 data showing production exceeding targets.
 - **Meat:** Production (8.71 M Mt) surpassed demand (around 7.6 M Mt) in 2022-23, creating surplus.
 - **Milk:** Production (14.07 M Mt in 2022-23) neared demand (14.33 M Mt), with minor shortages in some regions like Khulna.
 - **Eggs:** Production significantly higher than demand, creating a large surplus.
 - **Drivers:** Government policy, increased income, urbanization, and farmer investment boosted local sufficiency, reducing reliance on imports.
- Key Issues & Gaps (2024)
- **Food Safety:** Gaps identified in milk value chains, especially regarding farm registration, record-keeping for treatments, and heat stress management.
 - **Farm Practices:** Many small/medium farms lack formal registration, proper record-keeping, and advanced animal identification.
 - **Price & Inflation:** Rising input costs (like feed) and consumer prices for eggs and dairy were observed.
- Fodder:** Farmers adapt by using crop residues during shortages, but consistent fodder remains a challenge.

Livestock Economy at a Glance (2024-2025)

Table 1. Livestock population of Bangladesh (in lakh number)

Name of Species	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25
Cattle	237.85	239.35	240.86	242.38	243.91	245.45	247.00	248.56	250.13	251.71
Buffalo	14.71	14.78	14.79	14.86	14.93	15.00	15.08	15.16	15.24	15.32
Sheep	33.35	34.01	34.68	35.37	36.07	36.79	37.52	38.27	39.03	39.81
Goat	257.66	259.31	261.00	262.67	264.35	266.04	267.74	269.45	271.17	272.91
Total Ruminant	543.57	547.45	551.33	555.28	559.26	563.28	567.34	571.43	575.57	579.73

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Chicken	2683.93	2751.83	2821.45	2892.83	2966.02	3041.06	3118.00	3196.89	3277.77	3360.70
Duck	522.40	540.16	558.53	577.52	597.16	617.46	638.45	660.16	682.61	705.82
Total Poultry	3206.33	3292.00	3379.98	3470.35	3563.18	3658.52	3756.45	3857.04	3960.38	4066.52
Total Livestock	3749.90	3839.45	3931.31	4025.63	4122.44	4221.80	4323.79	4428.47	4535.95	4646.25

Table 2. Contribution of Livestock and Poultry in the National Economy of Bangladesh (2024-25)

Contribution of Livestock in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Constant Prices)	1.81 %
GDP growth rate of Livestock (Constant Prices)	3.19 %
Share of Livestock in Agricultural GDP (Constant prices)	16.54%
GDP volume (Current prices) (Crore Taka)	91,036
Employment (Directly)	20 %
Employment (Partly)	50 %

Table 3. Production of Milk, Meat and Eggs

Products	Unit	Fiscal Year									
		2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25
Milk	Lakh Metric Ton	72.75	92.83	94.01	99.23	106.80	119.85	130.74	140.68	150.44	155.38
Meat	Lakh Metric Ton	61.52	71.54	72.06	75.14	76.74	84.40	92.65	87.10	92.25	89.54
Egg	Crore number	1191.24	1493.31	1552.00	1711.00	1736.00	2057.64	2335.35	2337.63	2374.97	2440.65

Table 4. Demand, production and availability of milk, meat and eggs (2024-25)

Name of the Products	Demand	Production	Availability
Milk	2.33LakhMetricTon (ml/day/head)	(250)155.38LakhMetric Ton	239.29 (ml/day/head)
Meat	.92LakhMetricTon (gm/day/head)	(120)89.54LakhMetricTon	137.90 (gm/day/head)
Egg	1850.16Crorenumber (104number/year/head)	2440.65Crorenumbers	137.19 (number/year/head)

Table 5. Livestock contribution in GDP at Constant Price

Item (Base Year: 2015-16)	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25(p)
GDP (%)	2.17	2.07	2.06	1.98	1.91	1.85	1.83	1.81
Growth Rate of GDP (%)	2.90	3.01	3.19	2.94	3.10	3.17	3.07	3.19
Share of Livestock in Agricultural GDP (%)	16.51	16.48	16.45	16.40	16.45	16.37	16.35	16.54
GDP volume (Current prices) (Crore Taka)	39,624	43,212	46,673	50,301	67,398	73,665	81,897	91,036

Source: BBS, 2024-25; P denotes Provisional; Prepared by Dr. Hossan Md. Salim, Planning Section, Department of Livestock Services (DLS).

RATIONAL OF THE STUDY

Bangladesh is densely populated countries with limited land and water resources. Over 64.96% of the total population lives in the

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rural areas and highly dependent on agricultural system (World Bank 2016). The contribution of the livestock sub-sector to GDP currently 3.40% (2017-2018) Poultry industry is one of the major among livestock sub-sector that committed to supply cheap sources of good quality nutritious animal protein to the nation. Approximately, 20% of the protein consumption originates from poultry meat. Every house in village have some poultry for their subsidiary source of income. Poultry farms have grown up under private ownership having inadequate knowledge on reverse supply chain and ecological sustainability (Shamsuddoha, 2011b). Young generation is motivated to take it as main profession due to high competition in the job market. These young educated people are trying best to accept new technologies and concepts in their farming operation. Applications of such dynamic concepts easily guide them toward scientific farming with better profitability and sustainability. There are many works on the research of family poultry farming in Bangladesh but no work in Gopalganj district. So this study will help the poultry farmers to achieve success.

RESEARCH QUESTION

Every researcher must have some questions which is solved by using various analytical tools in any study. The current study contains a burning issue considering the poultry farming for profitability in the Gopalganj district. In the study area maximum families have poultry farming which improves their standards living of life. So the current study deals with profitability of family poultry farming and livelihood improvements through family poultry farming in Gopalgang district. The present study holds the following research questions:

- What is the present scenario of family poultry farming of some selected areas of Gopalganj district?
- What are the major areas in the Gopalganj district in volved with?
- How people cope with the challenges of poultry production in livestock sector?
- How researcher takes the analysis of economic effect and profitability of family poultry production?
- What are the problems and constraints in poultry production at home?

This research work will therefore be proffering to deal with the a fore mentioned questions while critically analyzing the collected data of the research.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The aim of this study is to analyze the condition of family poultry production. This study aims to provide information about cost and return of production and improvement on poultry farming. The result of this study may be helpful in making right decision for the growers. Again, it will help them to know about constraints which come in family poultry production and their solutions.

The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To analysis the socio-economic status of family poultry farmer in the study area.
2. To assess the profitability of poultry farming through cost and return of poultry farming.
3. To identify the problems faced by family poultry farmer and solutions associated with family poultry farming.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of literature in any research is essential because it provides opportunities for reviewing the stocks of knowledge and information for the research which gives a guideline in designing the future research problems. Some of important works regarding present study are reviewed here.

Aboki, E, A.A.U, Jongur and J.I, Onu (2013), conducted a study on productivity and technical efficiency of family poultry production in Kurmi local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria. This study assessed the socio-economic characteristics and technical efficiency of family poultry production in Kurmi Local Government Area of Taraba state, Nigeria. Findings from the study showed that female constitutes 60% of the family poultry producers in the study area. The result also reveals that the main reason for rearing family poultry is for sales. The technical efficiency estimate showed that the technical efficiency of family poultry ranges between 0.29 and 0.84, with a mean of 0.63. This indicates that on the average, the respondents are 63% efficient in the use of combination of their inputs. Return on investment (ROI) is 0.76 meaning that family poultry is highly profitable. This high profitability should attract financing by lending institutions.

Ahmed, M. F. U. (2001), made an economic analysis of broiler production under PROSHIKA supervision and private management. And he found that PROSHIKA provides better training to farmers under its supervision. And the trained farmers are skilled and their productivity is greater than the private management.

Begum, S. (2000), calculated cost and return of both broiler and layer firm. And found that both kinds of species provide benefit to farmers. And she said that poultry farming is a profitable business in Mymensingh district.

Md. Saidur Rahman, Habiba Pervin Halcyon (2012), made a socio-economic study on household poultry rearing in some selected areas of Mymensingh district in Bangladesh. The study is conducted to identify the socioeconomic characteristics of the household poultry farms and its impact on livelihood improvements. Sixty household poultry farmers were selected from Sadar upazila and Trishal upazila under Mymensingh district. Tabular as well as econometric methods were applied to analyze the data. Attempts were made to identify socio-economic characteristics, calculation of costs, returns, and find out the problems faced by the household poultry farmers. The study revealed that majority of the household poultry farmers were of the age group of 25-45 years and the high number had secondary education.

V P Nchinda, O Thieme*, P Ankers*, V Crespi and S Ariste (2006)**, conducted a study on food security and economic importance of family poultry (chicken) husbandry program in Artibonite and South departments of Haiti. The objective of this study was to determine the food security and economic importance of family poultry (chicken) husbandry intervention in the Artibonite and South departments of Haiti. Data were collected from 132 respondents following a quasi-experimental research design and triangulated using case studies findings of nine family poultry enterprises and secondary data of similar intervention in the areas covered. Data analysis was done using STATA version 10 and excel spreadsheet.

Julia de Bruyn, Johanna Wong, Brigitte Bagnol, Bruce Pengelly and Robyn Alders (2011), worked on family poultry and food and nutrition security. Family poultry production, which encompasses both extensive and small-scale intensive management systems, is practiced by many households in low-income food-deficit countries. Despite low production levels and potentially high losses due to disease, predation and theft, scavenging systems offer the advantage of requiring minimal land, labour and capital inputs.

K. M. A. Al-Mamun Rana, M. S. Rahman and M. N. Sattar (2012), determined the cost, return, and profitability of broiler production in some selected areas of Mymensingh district. They identified some problems in the production of broiler in the study area and finally give some recommendations for the development of broiler production in Bangladesh. It was mainly based on primary data which were collected through face-to-face interview from the respondents of broiler production during the month of December, 2011. Cobb-Douglas production function was also applied to explore the specific effect of the factors on broiler production.

M. S. Kabir, M. Asaduzzaman and D. S. Dev (2015), conducted a study on livelihood improvement through family poultry farming in Mymensingh district. His work shows that the family poultry farming creates a positive impact on the livelihood of the households in Bangladesh.

E. B. Sonaiya, R. D. S. Branckaert and E. F. Gueye (1999), worked on research and development options for family poultry. They show smallholder poultry production (i.e. family poultry) is an appropriate system that makes the best use of locally available resources.

Md. Nuru Miah (2003), conducted a study on family poultry production, a means of poverty eradication, self-employment and nutrition for the poor: Bangladesh experience. Family poultry production contributes an important role for the landless and small poor, 80 per cent of the total population who occupy average landholding size 0.05-2.49 acres.

Mohammad Shafiur Rahman Chowdhury and Md. Masud Chowdhury (2015), made an analysis to get profit ability analysis of poultry farming in Bangladesh: A case study on Trishal Upazilla in Mymensingh District. He also calculated the cost and benefit of family poultry farming and also the difficulties of poultry farming in household level. This study aimed to determine the cost, return, and profitability of broiler production in the based on primary data which were collected through well structured questionnaire from the respondents of poultry production during the month of October, 2014. Selected samples consisted of 80 poultry farm owners selected by using purposive sampling technique. In the selected area maximum people are related with agriculture. The findings revealed that poultry production was a profitable enterprise.

S.M. Billah, F.Nargis, M.E. Hossain, M.A.R. Howlider and S.H.Lee (2013), worked on family poultry production and consumption patterns in selected households in Bangladesh. Family poultry production accounts for most of the poultry production system in Bangladesh, but progress is not satisfactory. The present study assessed the existing poultry production and consumption patterns and constraints of poultry rearing of rural farmers in selected Northern areas of Bangladesh.

Nedup Dorji and Tshering Gyeltshen (2012), conducted a study on characterization of family poultry production in Haa and Mongar districts of Bhutan. The objective of the study was to characterize village chicken production of rural Bhutan. Moreover, chickens were mainly owned by women indicating poultry production at household level. The households kept flocks ranging from 2 to 24 birds per household with an average flock size of 7.40 ± 4.38 . The use of extension services was poor due to lack of awareness (71%) and poor services (5%). These results demonstrated that there is an increasing need to explore and implement research findings to improve poultry production that will contribute to reduce poverty in Bhutan - a rural phenomenon.

S M Fakhru Islam and M A Jabbar (2005), conducted a study on smallholder family poultry as a tool for poverty alleviation has been applied in Bangladesh. In this paper, the evolution of the model has been summarized and studies conducted to assess the impact of the poultry model at various stages of its evolution have been critically reviewed. Smallholder poultry as a tool for poverty alleviation has been developed and widely applied in Bangladesh. The results indicate that the project has reached the poor though not always ultra poor, the main target of the model, and that participants have benefited positively in terms of income, consumption and nutrition, empowerment of women. However, the results need to be assessed with a high degree of caution because of several methodological limitations of the impact studies.

R.A. Alabi and M.B. Aruna (2006), made an analysis on technical efficiency of family poultry production in Niger-Delta, Nigeria. This study assessed the technical efficiency of family poultry production in Niger- Delta, Nigeria. The technical efficiency estimates shows that the technical efficiency of family poultry ranges between 0.09 and 0.63, with mean of 0.22. This indicates that on the average, the respondents are 22% efficient in the use of combination of their inputs. The elasticity estimate of 12.29 indicates that the family poultry production is taking place at stage 1 (inefficient stage) in production curve. This study concludes that the output and technical efficiency of the family poultry production can be increased by the use of more feed, capital, medicine/vaccine and adoption of more innovations.

R.H. Dwinger, J.G. Bell and A. Permin (2014), lead a program to improve family poultry production in Africa. The Joint FAO/IAEA Division of the International Atomic Energy Agency has initiated a coordinated research program (CRP) to improve family poultry production in Africa. The program assists 12 scientists working in National Agricultural Research Systems (NARS) during a period of five years with research in the subject. Regular research coordination meetings bring together all participants involved in the program to exchange results and experiences and to adjust work plans and protocols. Initially, a standardized survey was used to assess the characteristics of family poultry production in 24 different farms in two ecological zones in each country during the wet and dry seasons.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The Study Area

The survey was conducted in Gopalganj Sadar Upazila in Gopalganj district in Bangladesh. The farmer of this area is casually dependent on agricultural production and they also focus mostly on poultry production. Beside agriculture gradually farmers are improving their lives through poultry farming. In the present study, the researcher selects the study areas with great care so that real results are representative. In selecting the sample areas, the researcher has to consider the limitation of his intellectual and financial capabilities and his time limitations. Thus, the present study was confined to Gopalganj district purposively. Then the researcher selects three union randomly from Sadar Upozila of the Gopalganj district. The name of the unions is respectively Gobra Union, Haridaspur, and Ulpur which is situated under Sadar Upazila.

Period of Data Collection

This research study is mainly based on primary data. Primary data has been collected from the selected sample villages between January and June, 2015 using a well-prepared questionnaire.

Analyzing and Editing of Data

Data were analyzed for achieving the objectives of the study. The filled-in interview schedules were scrutinized and the collected data were processed, edited and coded first.

a) Tabular technique: Tabular technique is well known and widely used technique. Tabular technique is the technique that is commonly followed to find out the crude association or difference between variables. In this study, tabular technique was followed to illustrate the whole picture of analysis. The tabular analysis was mainly based on Averages, percentages, frequencies, etc.

b) Graphical analysis: Graphical analysis was carried out to focus by bar diagram and pie chart of the rice farmers. In order to arrive at a meaningful result and so as to achieve the main objectives of the study, data were analyzed following graphical techniques.

Software Used in Analyzing Data

SPSS, MS word, MS excel, are used in analyzing data.

Multiple Regression Analysis

To assess the relationship between the profitability and resource use in the production process of family poultry Cobb-Douglas production function was used. Cobb-Douglas model was used to estimate the production function as

$\ln Y = \alpha + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + \beta_5 \ln X_5 + U_i$ Where,

Y=per farm gross return; X1= per farm bird cost; X2= per farm feed cost;

X3=per farm medic are cost; X4= per farm labor cost;

X5=Transportation and Marketing; B1.....β5= Estimated coefficient; α = Intercept; and

Ui= A random error term which are identically and independently distributed with mean0 and variance σ^2 i.e. $N(0, \sigma^2)$.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS

1. Age Distribution of the Respondents

All of the family of the study area were grouped into different age group is presented in Table 1. A table has shown below by comprising various age poultry farmers in the study area. The different age group of the poultry producers was examined by classifying the respondents into four age categories. These groups are 21-30 years, 31-40 years, 41-50 years, 51-60, and above 60 years.

Table 1: Age Distribution of the Respondents

Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
21-30	4	7
31-40	11	18
41-50	18	30
51-60	19	32
Above60	8	13
Total	60	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

From the table we see that out of total sampled family member about 7% belonged to the age group 21-30, about 18% belong the group 31-40, 30% belonged to the age group 41-50, 32% belonged to the age group 51-60 and about 13% belonged to the age group above 60.

The overall data collected from three unions of Gopalganj Sadar Upazilla are the sample unions, in which the average age of the respondent is reveals that the highest age distribution 32% from age group 51-60 and lowest 7% from age group 21-30. b tested to verify the relevance of the questions and the nature of response of sample procedures. After per-testing and necessary adjustment, a final survey schedule was developed.

2. Occupational Status of the Respondents in the Study Area

As we conducted the survey on family poultry farming so all of the 60 respondents have family poultry farm. It is found that, agriculture is the main occupational sources of livelihood and poultry farming is the subsidiary occupation of the selected respondents in the study areas. Mainly women in a family rare poultry and farmers make a poultry farm as their subsidiary income sources. Besides agriculture, some respondents are engaged in business and others sectors. Occupational status of the respondents is given in Table 5.5 below.

Table 2: Main Occupational Status of the Respondents

Name of Occupation	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Business	9	15
Agriculture	37	62
Laborer	8	13
Service	6	10
Total	60	100

Source: Field survey 2025

Table 2 refers to the occupational status of the respondent in the study area. It is found from the table that 62% respondents are engaged in agriculture as their main occupation. 15% respondents are engaged in business. 13% respondents are engaged as laborer. Only 10% respondents are engaged in other services as their main occupation. A figure related to occupational status of the respondents in the study area has shown below:

From the above figure it is clear that people in the study area are largely dependent on agriculture. About 62% respondents are involved in agriculture. Service holders are in less proportion.

3. Types of Housing of the Respondents in the Study Area

Table 3 indicates the house type of the respondents in the study area. It is found from the study area that majority of houses of respondents in the study area are found to be tin shed. A table of house type of the respondents in the study area has shown below:

Table 3: Types of House of the Respondents

House Type	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Tin-shed	42	70
Brick built	17	28
Fences	1	2
Mud	0	0
Total	60	100

Source: Field survey 2025

From the above table we get that about 70% houses are tin-shed and about 28% houses are brick built and only about 2% houses are made by fences. There are no mud houses in the study areas. A figure related to types of houses of the respondents in the study area has shown below:

The figure shows that majority of the respondents have tin-shed house, 70% are their portion on the above figure. Only 2% have mud house.

4. Duration of the Poultry Farming in the Study Area

Table 4 indicates the experiences of the respondent in the study area. It is found from the study area that majority of poultry farmers in the study area are found to be experienced. A table indicates the duration of poultry production of the poultry farmers in the study area has shown below:

Table.4: Experience of the Respondents

Type	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Experienced	43	72
Un-experienced	17	28
Total	60	100

Source: Field survey 2025

Among 60 respondents 43 respondents are previously experienced and 17 are un-experienced because they are starting their farming this year. A figure about the experiences of the respondents is given below:

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This diagram shows that maximum respondents are experienced. About 72% respondents are experienced and about 28% are un-experienced.

5. Training Facilities of the Respondents

As it is a survey based on family poultry farming so they do not need any formal training, But some farmers take formal training for comparatively large farm. Table 5 is given below:

Table 5: Training Facilities of the Respondents

Type	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Trained	8	13
Untrained	52	87
Total	60	100

Source: Field survey 2025

Table 5 points out the training facilities of the respondents. About 87% respondents are untrained and only 13% are trained.

This figure indicates maximum respondents are untrained. As they have small poultry farm in their house so they need not to take

training.

6. Monthly Income of the Respondents

In the study, the sample members are divided into five income groups, according to their monthly income, viz .0-5000 Tk, 5000-10000Tk, 10000-15000Tk,15000-20000Tk, and above 20000 Tk. The different income groups are given below in Table 6

Table 6: Monthly Income of the Respondents

Income (Tk.)	No. of Respondents	Percentage
0-5000	7	12
5000-10000	26	43
10000-15000	17	28
15000-20000	10	17
Above 20000	0	0
Total	60	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

From the table it is shown that 12% of the respondents are fall in the income group 0- 5000, 43% of the respondents are fall in the income group 5000-10000, 28% respondents are fall in the income group 10000-15000, 17% of the respondents are fall in the income group 15000-20000, and there is no respondents in the income group above 20000. This can be shown in the following figure.

From the above figure we can say that maximum respondents earn their income around 5000-10000 Tk and the area is indicated by the proportion of 43%. There are no income earners above 20000 Tk.

7. Monthly Expenditure of Respondents in the Study Area

In the study, the sample members are divided into five expenditure groups, according to their monthly expenditure, viz. 0-5000 Tk, 5000-10000 Tk, 10000-15000 Tk, 15000- 20000 Tk, and above 20000 Tk. The different expenditure groups are given below in Table 7

Table 7: Expenditure of Respondents in the Study Area

Expenditure range (Tk.)	No. of Respondents	Percentage
0-5000	8	13
5000-10000	36	60
10000-15000	9	15
15000-20000	7	12
Above 20000	0	0
Total	60	100

Source: Field Survey2025

From the table it is shown that 13% of the respondents are fall in the expenditure group 0-5000, 60% of the respondents are fall in the income group 5000-10000, 15% respondents are fall in the income group 10000-15000, 12% of the respondents are fall in the income group 15000-20000, and there is no respondents in the expenditure group above 20000.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Introduction

The main purpose of this chapter is to determine the profitability of family poultry farming and farmer’s livelihood improvement through it. Impact of family poultry on the household, analysis of impacts on livelihood improvement of family poultry farming.

Cost, Return and Profitability Analysis

In the study to analyze their profitability the costs and returns of family poultry are estimated. The cost items include: housing, tools and equipment, birds purchasing cost, feed cost, labor cost, transportation and marketing cost and interest on operating capital. The resource of family poultry included returns from eggs and bird sales. Total cost, gross returns, net returns and benefit-cost ratio have been determined and discussed.

Costs

The cost items were classified into two broad categories, i.e. (i) Fixed costs and (ii) Variable costs. Family poultry production includes different types of costs under the following heads.

(i) Fixed Cost

Housing cost: Some poultry house found within the living house and some were outside of living houses found in the study. By using old tins, iron sheets, woods, bamboos and plastic bags the outside poultry living houses are often made.

Tools and equipment cost: Various tools and equipment like cooking pots, water jar, egg cage, plastic bowls, clay pots and tin cans are used for feeding and drinking. By applying straight-line depreciation method the cost for tools and equipment was determined for one year. The annual depreciation cost was calculated as follows:

Depreciation = (Original value-salvage value)/Life of the asset **Table 8: Annual Average Costs of Family Poultry**

Items of cost	Taka	Percentage of total cost
Variable cost		
Feed cost	913	23.53
Cost of birds	350	9.02

Medicare cost	226	5.82
Labor cost	1553	40.02
Transport & marketing	200	5.15
Interest on capital	172.26	4.44
Sub total	3414.26	
Fixed cost		
Depreciation on housing	322	8.30
Depreciation on equipment	144.23	3.72
Sub total	466.23	
Total cost	3880.49	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Benefit Cost Ratio

Return per taka invested is implied by the term Benefit Cost Ratio. It represents the financial feasibility of any farm. In the present study, the value of BCR was 1.95. So, the family poultry farming is profitable and financially efficient.

Table 9 : Gross return, gross margin, and net return of family poultry

Particular	Taka
Chicken and egg	
Sold Consumed	
Total(sold+ consumed)	3275
	1967
	5242
Value of present stock	2340
Gross return{(sold + consumed) +value of present stock}	7582
Total variable cost(TVC) Total cost(TC)	3414.26
Gross margin(gross return - TVC) Net return (gross return–total cost)	3880.49
Benefit-cost ratio(gross return/total cost)	4567.74
	4101.51
	1.95

Profitability Analysis

Cobb-Douglas production function was employed to investigate the factors affecting production of family poultry through production function analysis because in the Cobb- Douglas production function, the regression coefficients directly represent production elasticity and as all the sum of the production elasticity indicate whether the production process as an increasing, constant, or decreasing returns to scale.

Table 10: Estimated Values of Coefficient and their Related Statistics for Cobb-Douglas Production Function

Variables	Estimated coefficient	t-statistic
Bird cost(X_1)	0.36**	3.45
Feed cost(X_2)	0.48**	7.12
Medicare cost(X_3)	0.21*	1.26
Labor cost(X_4)	0.27	2.41
Transportation and Marketing cost(X_5)	0.16	1.23
Intercept	2.28	4.87
R^2	0.88	
Adjusted R^2	0.79	
F-value	218.56	
Returns to scale	1.54	

Notes: ** Significant at 1 percent probability level, * Significant at 5 percent probability level. Source: Field survey authors estimation, 2025.

It appears from Table 6.3 that the estimated coefficients of the Cobb-Douglas model. It also appears from table that the regression coefficients of bird and feed for family poultry were positive and significant at 1 percent level of significant. Labor for family poultry was positive and significant at 5 per cent level of significance.

One percent increase in bird cost and feed cost keeping other factors constant would result in increase in the gross returns by 0.36 and 0.48 percent for family poultry farm, respectively indicated by the result of the analysis. The transportation and marketing cost have positive effect on production, but in the study area farmers usually have little transportation and marketing cost. Generally, they used to go to the village market by walk. For that reason, this important variable is insignificant. In the study area,

The F-value of the equation is significant at 1 percent level of confidence implying that the variation in poultry farms depends mainly on the key explanatory variables included in the model. The overall performance of the Cobb-Douglas model for family poultry was satisfactory as indicated by the estimated R^2 and F-values.

The estimated regression coefficients of Cobb-Douglas production represent the coefficient of elasticity of production. The returns to scale are said to be constant if the sum of these of the regression coefficient is equal to unity, increasing if the sum of the regression is greater than unity and decreasing if the sum is less than unity. In the present study the returns to scale of poultry farm was computed by the sum of regression coefficients of poultry farm that were presented in the Table 6.2. The sum of elasticity of conventional inputs stood at 1.54 for poultry farms. It was observed that the summation of elasticity of different inputs for poultry farms was positive and greater than one, implying that the production function exhibited increasing returns.

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS

From the major findings of the study, it can be concluded that family poultry farming as a secondary occupation is comparatively profitable. Socioeconomic wellbeing of family poultry farming in the study area is amazing, found to be very well and satisfactory. Therefore, it can be concluded from the above discussion that family poultry production is profitable. A considerable scope patently exists to increase the productivity of family poultry farm, therefore income, employment, nutritional status and overall livelihood status of farmers in the study area as well as other potential areas in Bangladesh. It also helps to ameliorate the problem of gender issue by enabling the women to participate in income generation activities and household decision making process in rural areas. The management practices of family poultry farming in the study area were not found efficient enough. Farmers were not known about the application of inputs in right time with right doses. Consequently, they made over or under use of some inputs. There are further scopes to increase the productivity by introducing scientific method. Efficient and planned management training in accordance with their problems, needs, goals and resource base can lead to viable production practices and sustainable income.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Family poultry rearing have been practiced for a longtime in Bangladesh. Family poultry plays a significant role in the nutrition enhancement, income generation, self-employment, poverty eradication, women empowerment and improving the livelihood of small farmers. The study found the benefit cost ratio of 1.95 from family poultry, which indicated that family poultry rearing is profitable venture and a yearly net return of Tk. 4105.51. The production function analysis indicates that 1 percent increase in bird and feed cost keeping other factors constant would result in increase in the gross returns by

0.36 percent and 0.48 percent for family poultry farm, respectively. It provides employment to the women at both the on and off season of crop farming. Overall it changed food habit, improved family health and sanitation, increased savings and enhanced women empowerment of the poultry farmers. Now-a-days family poultry faces several economic, social and natural, marketing and technical problems. To solve these problems ensuring training on disease control, housing, equipment, feeding, genetic improvement and marketing, availing feed availability, credit facility and good parent stock by the government and non-government organizations were the suggested measures by the farmers.

The farmers put forward following suggestions to overcome these problems of family poultry rearing and to make family poultry farming more profitable: They must be ensured stable and reasonable price of poultry and providing price incentives. To get rid of the problem of shortage of fund, short term loan for poultry farming should be made on easy terms and conditions by government and NGO's. Most of the respondents suggested that government should increase veterinary services by supplying necessary vaccine and medicine at lower price and by establishing new veterinary care centers. Social security should be provided and awareness about poultry should be developed. Government and mass media should take initiatives to reduce information gap to reduce diseases. Government should take steps to provide training among farmers about poultry rearing. Most of the farmers suggested that there should be proper training facilities on family poultry production as it will increase their ability to do poultry farming work properly.

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